

Why Mixed Methods Matter: Defending an Integrated Approach to Understanding the Complexities of Implementing Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in Higher Education using a Case Study

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This paper focuses on the methodological strategy employed in a case study exploring lecturers' perspectives on Universal Design for learning (UDL) to support inclusion in higher education. The purpose is to demonstrate the value of mixed methods in answering the study's research questions. UDL implementation is framed as a policy priority to widen access and respond more effectively to diversity through inclusive teaching practices. Pragmatism and constructivism provided the philosophical underpinning to the study offering methodological flexibility to support a mixed -methods case study design. An initial survey identified quantitative trends and patterns followed by focus groups which explained and expanded on these findings enabling triangulation and corroboration across three data sources to enhance the validity and credibility of the study's findings. The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR), an evidence-based implementation science framework served as the analytical lens. CFIR supported a systematic identification of enablers and barriers to UDL implementation as perceived by lecturers. Emerging findings indicate lecturers' belief in UDL and significant effort towards more inclusive practices. While University backing is a motivational factor, the analysis reveals that leadership at the level closest to pedagogical practice is essential to alignment in teaching, learning and assessment. The findings indicate a need for meaningful professional learning and development on UDL, protected time and opportunities for collaboration, peer support, mentoring and sharing practice. Overall, the study demonstrates how a mixed-methods, CFIR informed approach can generate a nuanced understanding of UDL offering methodological and practical insights for implementation within higher education contexts.

Keywords: UDL, Higher Education, Mixed Methods, Triangulation, Data synthesis, CFIR.

Highlights

- Defending mixed methods as a research approach to gain credible and meaningful insights into how lecturers in one HEI understand and practice UDL.
- Demonstrating alignment of philosophy, methodology and methods to support credible findings and address critiques of MMR.
- Using CFIR as an evidence-based analytical framework to explore the range of factors influencing UDL implementation as perceived by lecturers.

Introduction & Rationale

Policymakers in Ireland advocate for UDL implementation across the higher education sector to widen access to higher education to priority groups, equalize participation, and eliminate barriers to learning (HEA, 2023; Healy, Banks & Ryder, 2024). Grounded in neuroscience, educational psychology, and inclusive pedagogy (Rose & Meyer, 2002), UDL seeks to create flexible learning environments that accommodate learners' diverse needs in the design, delivery, and assessment of academic content.

While discursive framing frequently positions UDL as both attainable and transformative, the evidence demonstrates that practical enactment within higher education is far from straightforward (Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2021; Luo and Kirsh 2023; AHEAD, 2024; Morina *et al.*, 2025). UDL implementation, even when framed in normative terms, is thought to be shaped and constrained by contextual conditions, institutional policies, culture, leadership, educator beliefs, and pedagogical practices (Martin, 2021; Ewe & Galvin, 2023; Timus *et al.*, 2023; Şeker, 2024; Morina *et al.*, 2025).

In view of the foregoing, this paper shifts attention to the methodological approach adopted in a mixed methods case study exploring lecturers' perspectives on UDL implementation for inclusive teaching, learning and assessment. The case, situated within a single campus of a multi-campus technological university (TU) involved participants from two academic departments in student facing roles. In 2025 the University became a signatory to ALTITUDE - the National Charter on Universal Design for Learning in Tertiary Education formalising its commitment to UD and UDL implementation across all its functions,

The paper provides a robust and theoretically grounded rationale for the choice of a mixed methods approach to foreground the lecturer voice on UDL implementation. While it does not address the research questions directly, it demonstrates how mixed methods offered a superior framework to address a complex question in education. At a time when higher education policy is focused on supporting institutions to respond more effectively to increased student diversity, the lecturer voice, examined through a mixed-methods lens, is critical to understanding how inclusive pedagogies like UDL are understood and enacted in practice. Harnessing the strengths of quantitative and qualitative methods while offsetting their respective limitations was a compelling justification to use this approach to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: How do lecturers understand and implement UDL as the foremost educational framework to support inclusion in higher education?

RQ2: To what extent are lecturers motivated to integrate UDL guidelines into their teaching, learning and assessment practices?

RQ3: What inclusive teaching, learning and assessment strategies do lecturers use or wish to use and what factors influence their motivation to do so?

RQ4: What are the key enablers and barriers to lecturers' integrating UDL into their practice?

The next section explores the philosophy that underpins mixed methods research. It clarifies the epistemological stance that guided the study to demonstrate congruence between the researcher's world view and the methodology used. It also addresses critiques of MMR, acknowledging the ongoing debate about its limitations, as well as the critique of pragmatism as a sufficient rationale to justify integrating quantitative and qualitative inquiry. This is followed by a comprehensive outline of the study's trajectory to highlight the importance in mixed methods of a rigorous approach to research design as well as meticulous attention to all stages of the research process.

Philosophical Assumptions in Mixed Methods Research

Philosophy in research is understood to relate to the beliefs, assumptions and principles that underpin a study and provide "an illuminating roadmap for the researcher" (Sefotho, 2015, p.23). Philosophy and paradigms share a common focus in the underlying influence of ontology, epistemology, and methodology (Scotland, 2012.) Although paradigms represent the researcher's worldview and provide a means "to study selected aspects of the world" (Salomon, 1991, p.15) a crucial aspect of the research process is the fit between assumptions and the perceived nature of the phenomenon under investigation. This alignment is essential to determine the type of questions to be asked and the methodology to be used.

Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) posit that the underpinning philosophy in mixed methods studies should be explicit to provide coherence and methodological integrity. While pragmatism provides the overarching stance for this mixed methods study, a constructivist epistemology informs the interpretation of participants' experience within

the qualitative phase. Pragmatism emphasizes the value of combining methods to address complex research questions comprehensively and effectively. This philosophy is congruent with the researcher's epistemology and ontological stance which favours methodological flexibility and a focus on practical solutions to real world problems. Considering this, the case study employed an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach to data collection, analysis and interpretation underpinned by an overarching pragmatist philosophy which emphasised methodological flexibility, and a 'what works' approach to answering complex questions and achieving practical outcomes (Denscombe, 2017). The overarching goal in adopting this methodological strategy was to triangulate and synthesise data from three data types to deliver in-depth critical insights into lecturers' perspectives on UDL implementation shedding light on their subjective experiences and nuanced viewpoints. As central participants in higher education teaching, learning and assessment, the lecturer voice is indispensable to understanding the challenges and opportunities inherent in translating UDL policy into practice.

In alignment with the methodological literature, quantitative data obtained from a small sample size, bounded within the case context, was not intended to provide generalisable findings. Rather the quantitative findings served to identify patterns and trends which guided, informed and enhanced the explanatory power of the subsequent qualitative phase. This is well established in mixed-methods literature and serves as a caution to mixed method researchers about the necessity for consistency between sampling and the type of generalisation made (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009; Fetters, Curry and Creswell, 2013; Plano Clark and Ivankova, 2016; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Hong and Fabregues, 2025). While qualitative methods provide contextualised and nuanced accounts, their integration with quantitative findings allows researchers to generate deeper and more comprehensive explanations of complex questions. The methodological literature consistently notes that integration is a central tenet of mixed methods research that enhances explanatory power (Fetters, Curry and Creswell, 2013), yields richer and more robust interpretations (Bazeley, 2018), and produces more complete understanding than either approach alone (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Complementarity between the breadth of quantitative data and the depth of qualitative insight enables the elaboration, clarification, and illumination of complex questions (Greene, 2007; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). The next section addresses the contested nature of mixed methods research as revealed by the scholarly literature.

Addressing Critiques of MMR

Since the 1980s, there has been a growing interest in MMR among researchers who are not persuaded by the purist stance exemplified by Kuhn's (1970) argument, particularly in the social sciences. However, polemical debate continues unabated over the suitability of pragmatism as the only philosophical underpinning for mixed methods studies (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Feilzer, 2010; Hall, 2013; Shan, 2021).

Hampson and McKinley (2023) expose deficiencies in pragmatism as a guiding framework for mixed methods studies because it offers no set methodological requirements for researchers to follow to ensure the quality of their own research or to evaluate the work of others. Hong and Fàbregues (2025) critically reflect on the lack of attention in the literature to the fundamental issue of generalisation in MMR. Similarly, O'Donoghue and Farrelly (2024) highlight a lack of methodological rigour and the erroneous use of the term 'mixed methods' in published research papers. These authors emphasise the need for researchers to pay close attention to coherence between epistemological commitments, methodology and methods. Their findings reveal many instances of published research that profess to be mixed methods research in which there is little evidence of any substantive mixing in the research practices used. In the absence of any synthesis of results, what researchers claim are mixed methods studies can be more accurately described as parallel or concurrent studies.

Although the focus of O'Donoghue and Farrelly's critique is interpretative research conducted within mixed methods studies, they highlight issues that were salient to the present study including the case study approach, triangulation, and use of the term 'perspectives' in mixed methods studies. Exploring the lecturer voice on UDL implementation through a mixed methods case study aimed to generate thick descriptions that captured detailed insights and the contextual nuances of the participants' experiences. This may not have been achieved had the researcher used a singular method. As Salomon (1991) stated "this type of cohabitation is not a luxury; it is a necessity if any fruitful outcomes are ever expected to emerge" (p.17).

Methods

The methodological approach adopted in the case study pursued two objectives. The first was to produce valid and credible findings capable of informing inclusive teaching policy and practice within the faculties targeted in this study. The second was to

demonstrate the strength of an integrated, coherent, and philosophically aligned mixed methods design in generating comprehensive insights and a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

In alignment with the literature on how to conduct sequential explanatory case studies, using a mixed methods approach (Stake, 1995; Yazan, 2015; Cohen *et al.*, 2018; Mertens, 2020) the quantitative phase preceded the qualitative inquiry. The initial quantitative survey instrument collected objective data from a sample of lecturers (n=58) within two faculties on their understanding and practice of UDL. A subsequent qualitative phase explained and elaborated on the quantitative findings using three structured focus groups (n=21).

The findings from the quantitative phase directly informed the design of the qualitative instrument: specific focus group questions allowed participants to explore, expand, and explain several key findings in more depth. The purposeful integration of methods and mixing of data was central to the sequential design employed in the study. This design not only supported methodological rigour but also ensured alignment with the fundamental principles of mixed methods research, acknowledging its strength and suitability as an approach to address complex questions in the evolving higher education landscape.

Yin (2018) acknowledges the value of mixed methods within case study research, recognizing the need for multiple sources of evidence to strengthen the study's reliability and validity. Building on this, Nair *et al.*, (2023) show that a mixed-methods within-case design achieves this by integrating qualitative and quantitative data inside a single case, enabling comparative analysis across the case's internal units.

The underdeveloped evidence base for UDL implementation within higher education (Capp, 2017; Duncan *et al.*, 2025) allowed this approach to identify themes which could be compared or aligned with existing studies on UDL implementation in tertiary education. In this way, the case study aimed to add to the knowledge base on UDL practices in higher education, especially those that privilege the voices of academics tasked with enacting the policy at the coal face. Exploring how lecturers understand and practice UDL and their views about the barriers they face integrating policy guidelines in practice, aimed to contribute to both theory-building and implementation knowledge in the HEI studied.

Ethical Considerations

In alignment with rigorous institutional guidelines and the centrality of ethical imperatives in mixed methods studies (Greene, 2007; Mertens, 2007; Cresswell and Plano Clark, 2018) the researcher adhered to established ethical standards across all stages of the research process. Participants were provided with comprehensive details about the research, including the purpose of the study, how data would be collected, managed, and stored and the measures in place to protect participants' rights. These were outlined in the plain language statement (PLS) and the informed consent form (ICF). For both phases of the data collection, informed consent was obtained from the participants. The survey respondents were required to indicate that they had read and understood the informed consent before they could complete the questionnaire and focus group participants were required to sign the informed consent form before the recorded discussions could commence. Participants were informed that they were free to withdraw their consent at any stage during the data collection process with no consequences whatsoever. Confidentiality and data protection were strictly maintained throughout the study. Survey responses were collected using a fully anonymous online survey. Focus groups recordings were transcribed verbatim and fully anonymised during transcription. All data were stored on a password protected institutional server and accessed only by the researcher.

Insider Research

The researcher's position as an insider researcher working within the HEI setting where the study was conducted was a key consideration in this study. As noted by Mercer (2007) and Unluer (2012), insider researchers must navigate the complexities of dual roles, organisational relationships and contextual familiarity. If these aspects are not managed carefully at all stages of the process, the credibility and validity of the study's findings may be at risk. The literature also highlights the fluid and dynamic nature of insider-outsider status, emphasising that positionality is contingent and can shift throughout the research process (Hellowell 2006;). Greene (2014) and Berger (2015) similarly argue that insider research entails an ongoing process of positionality, in which researchers acknowledge and analyse how their identities, knowledge, experiences and assumptions influence and shape the research process and outcomes.

To mitigate the risks of familiarity and potential bias, the study employed several established procedures in qualitative research. Reflexivity was central, supported by bracketing to identify and suspend preconceptions and prior knowledge (Tufford and Newman, 2012; McLeod, 2024). Reflexive journaling was used during key stages of data collection to monitor collegial relationships ensuring that an objective analytical stance was maintained. During data analysis reflexive journaling documented emerging findings and interpretative decisions. Additional measures included triangulation of data sources, the use of an independent moderator for the focus groups, member checking focus group transcripts to ensure accuracy and peer review of emerging findings.

While insider research presents ethical challenges, it also afforded significant advantages including contextual knowledge and ready access to gatekeepers and participants. These combined strategies helped ensure the rigour, transparency and ethical integrity of the study at all stages.

Data Analysis

The data in this study were drawn from three data sets: quantitative survey findings, open-ended survey responses, focus group data. Together, these datasets provided complementary and sometimes contradictory insights into lecturers' perspectives on UDL implementation addressing the study's four research questions. The findings were organised around five inductively derived themes which were generated through systematic thematic analysis (Naeem *et al.*, 2023) and supported by the initial survey findings. The synthesised data was then mapped to CFIR, the study's overarching analytical framework.

Phase 1 Quantitative Data: Survey Questionnaires

The convenience sample in Phase 1 was a subset of the specific population under investigation in the study. In this way, it was clearly delineated. The sample consisted of 58 lecturers and included lecturers at early, mid and late career stages with a balanced gender distribution between male and female participants. Participants were from two faculties in one campus, and they were invited by their line-manager, acting as gatekeeper, to participate in a fully anonymous online survey questionnaire on a voluntary and informed basis. The survey instrument was used to collect quantitative data in Phase 1 of the study. The data generated was analysed using IBM's statistical software SPSS to capture general trends and emerging patterns regarding lecturers' knowledge,

awareness, and practices of UDL as well as their perspectives on inclusion and disability in higher education. A range of statistical tests was conducted to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings. These included descriptive statistics to summarise key trends in the data. Cronbach alpha was used to assess the internal consistency of multi-item scales; Pearson's correlation and Spearman's rank order correlation examined relationships between key variables. These tests were selected to account for the distribution and scale of the data and to provide a robust foundation for identifying themes that would subsequently be explained and elaborated upon during the qualitative phase. The patterns and relationships uncovered in this phase were purposefully used to guide the development of the focus group questions, thereby ensuring data integration in line with a mixed methods design.

Phase 2 Qualitative Data: Open Survey Responses and Focus Groups

Rich qualitative data were generated from the open survey questions and three focus groups (n=21) in Phase 2 of the study necessitating a rigorous and systematic approach to data analysis. Systematic thematic analysis (STA) informed by Naeem *et al.*, 2023 was selected as the most suitable process to use due to its structured and sequential approach to analysing data. The approach comprises six key stages: (1) familiarisation with the data through repeated reading (2) extraction of keywords that captured recurrent ideas within the dataset; (3) coding of quotation using keywords to organise data meaningfully; (4) development of themes by clustering related codes; (5) interpretive conceptualisation in which themes were examined for underlying patterns and explanatory value; and (6) the synthesis of these elements into a conceptual model grounded in the data (Naeem *et al.*, 2023). In this study, this staged approach enabled consistent and comparative analysis of open survey responses and focus group data contributing to the development of themes that were both grounded in participant accounts and responsive to the explanatory role of mixed methods studies. In addition, STA's capacity to systematically map qualitative themes to the CFIR framework was particularly useful in ruling out other methods of analysis that were initially considered.

Analytical Framework – CFIR

The analytical framework in this study was CFIR (Damschroder *et al.*, 2009). This is a well-established, evidence-based framework to study the interrelated factors

influencing how new practices are adopted and implemented in different settings. In 2022, CFIR was updated based on extensive user feedback to enhance its overall practical applicability, usability, and effectiveness (Damschroder *et al.*, 2022).

CFIR assesses implementation across five domains including: Intervention Characteristics, Outer Setting, Inner Setting, Characteristics of Individuals and Implementation Process. CFIR thus provided a useful lens to examine the complexity of UDL implementation in a higher education setting and in alignment with a mixed methods approach, CFIR was used in both phases of data collection. In Phase 1, the survey questions were linked to relevant CFIR domains to capture the broad perspectives of lecturers on their understanding and practice of UDL as well as perceived institutional support and barriers to implementation. In Phase 2, the focus group instrument was also structured around CFIR to deeply explore several key findings in the quantitative data. CFIR enabled continuity in approach between both phases of data collection ensuring they were meaningfully connected and conceptually aligned.

Applying CFIR as a coding framework for the qualitative inquiry, systematic thematic analysis identified the enablers and barriers to UDL implementation as perceived by lecturers. The structured nature of CFIR ensured that themes emerging from the qualitative inquiry were interpreted within a robust implementation science framework enhancing the study's ability to generate relevant insights into how UDL is interpreted and enacted by lecturers in higher education. This systematic alignment facilitated purposeful integration of three data types addressing the criticism of minimal or superficial mixing in many studies purporting to be mixed methods identified by O'Donoghue & Farrelly (2024).

Limitations

Acknowledging the study's limitations contributes to transparency by highlighting the boundaries of the research and its capacity for wider interpretation and generalisability. The researcher acknowledged that these limiting factors – including a small sample, potential biases in self-reported data and the challenges inherent in designing and executing a mixed methods study had the potential to undermine the validity of the case study's findings. However, the researcher proactively sought to mitigate these risks paying close attention to the study design, the purposeful integration

of quantitative and qualitative data at all stages of the research process, triangulating data from different sources drawing on the evidence from the literature (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018; Creswell, 2022; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; O'Donoghue and Farrelly, 2024) and rigorously applying the established measures to ensure trustworthiness in mixed methods research.

Conclusion

This paper has used methodological literature to justify the use of a mixed methods case study underpinned by a pragmatist and constructivist methodology to deeply explore lecturers' perspectives on UDL implementation in one HEI setting. It presented a robust rationale for the use of a mixed methods approach combining objective insights with deep, subjective experiences to illuminate the complexity of the phenomena studied.

The paper argues that mixed methods matter when careful integration and data synthesis generate more complete, robust and analytically rich interpretations than is possible from one method alone. Integrating quantitative and qualitative inquiry within a single case study aimed to gain a more complete understanding of lecturers' perspectives on UDL implementation identifying the bridges and barriers within a robust implementation science framework.

The emerging findings yielded both convergence as well as dissonance lending more credibility to study's findings. The divergence revealed the underlying complexities and tensions inherent in translating UDL policy into practice and underscored the methodological superiority of mixed methods in capturing the complexity of inclusive teaching practices in higher education.

Overall, this article has demonstrated that careful attention to the research design, sampling strategy, the sequence of data collection, the purposeful mixing of data at all stages of the research process, enabled mixed methods within a case study to yield credible and valid findings. The researcher's hope is that this study contributes meaningfully to the discourse on UDL in higher education, informing sustainable implementation by harnessing the bridges and addressing the barriers as identified by lecturers, central participants in teaching, learning and assessment. A further aspiration is that this study dispels any doubt over the value and legitimacy of mixed methods in educational research.

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